

A New Saponin from the Seeds of *Heterophragma quadriloculare*

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Manuscript received 10 April 1989, revised 5 December 1991, accepted 1 April 1992

*H. quadriloculare*¹ (Bignoniaceae) occurs in M.P., Deccan and Southern region of the country. The roots of the plant are reported to be useful in snake-bite.

The air-dried powdered and defatted seeds (2 kg) of *H. quadriloculare* were extracted with 95% ethanol for several hours. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and to it was added large amount of acetone to get a precipitate which was separated by filtration. The process of dissolution in alcohol and precipitation by acetone was repeated several times to get a light brown amorphous powder which gave all the tests for saponins². On tlc examination, it showed single spot which was purified by column chromatography over silica-gel G and crystallised as brown needles from acetone-ethanol (1 : 1), C₄₀H₈₈O₁₀, M⁺ 698, m.p. 141–42°; its acetyl derivative, C₄₂H₈₀O₁₁, m.p. 139–40°, acetyl (5.4%), M⁺ 740; its $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 380, 2 905, 1 640, 1 450, 1 380, 1 130, 1 065, 1 025, 998, 955, 840 and 805 cm⁻¹ and ¹H nmr spectra of acetyl derivative of the glucoside δ (CDCl₃; TMS) at 0.75 (3H, s, CH₃-18), 0.67 (6H, dd, J 6,6,2, secondary CH₃ at 25, 26), 0.72 (3H, d, J 5.2 Hz, CH₃-20), 0.78 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₃ of rhamnose), 0.82 (3H, m-CH₃-27), 1.34–1.92 (29H, complex pattern for polymethylene CH₂ and CH), 2.12 (3H, s, OAc-3), 2.02, 2.04, 2.05, 2.06, 2.08, 2.10 (6-OAc of glucose and rhamnose), 3.52–4.25 (4H, m, protons of glucose), 4.35 (1H, d, J 5.6 Hz, 1'-anomeric proton), 4.46 (1H, t, H-3), 4.56–4.68 (4H, m, protons of rhamnose), 5.48 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, anomeric proton) and 5.50 (1H, dd, J 4.5, 8.5 Hz, H-6).

On hydrolysis with 7% H₂SO₄, it afforded a

genin, m.p. 156–57°, [α]_D²⁵ – 31.6, C₂₈H₄₈O, M⁺ 400, crystallised from ethanol-acetone (1 : 1) as colourless needles. It formed an acetate, m.p. 158–59°, [α]_D²⁵ = 9.1 (CHCl₃), C₃₀H₅₂O₂, M⁺ 442; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400, 2 905, 1 635, 1 450, 1 390, 1 130, 1 065, 1 025, 998, 955, 840 and 810 cm⁻¹; m/z 400, 385, 382, 315 and 230. It was identified as 24-methylcholest-5-ene-3β-ol (m.p., m.m.p., co-pc and tlc) with authentic samples. The hydrolysate was neutralised with BaCO₃ and BaSO₄ and was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated to a brown viscous mass and was found to contain two sugars, D-glucose and L-rhamnose³ (co-pc and co-tilc) with authentic samples. Permethylation⁴ of the saponin followed by acid hydrolysis yielded 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose, thereby confirming that C₁ of the rhamnose was involved in the glycosylation. Periodate oxidation⁵ of the saponin suggested that both the sugars are present in the pyranose form.

Partial hydrolysis of the saponin with Killiani mixture liberated D-glucose followed by L-rhamnose, suggesting that D-glucose was the terminal sugar and L-rhamnose was attached to genin. Enzyme emulsin⁶ hydrolysis confirmed the presence of β-linkage between L-rhamnose and the genin and hydrolysis with the enzyme tokadiastase confirmed α-linkage between D-glucose and the L-rhamnose. Therefore, sapogenin was linked at C₁ of the L-rhamnose via β-linkage and C₄ of the L-rhamnose was attached to the C₁ of the D-glucose via α-linkage. Thus saponin was identified as 24-methylcholest-5-en-3-O-α-D-glucoside (1 → 4)-O-β-L-rhamnoside.

NOTES

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.D.R.I., Lucknow for recording the spectra and one of the authors (A.K.J.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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